

IPAD-MD

Deliverable 5.1 (WP5)

Survey on Patient Organisations' Research Priorities

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Deliverable 5.2 (WP5)

Summary Report on the Engagement with Stakeholder Organisations

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1. Survey on Patient Organisations' Research Agendas

Introduction

The main objectives of IPAD-MD Work Package 5 – Engagement with Patient Organisations are to identify relevant patient organisations and advocacy groups on the national, European and international scale and to identify potential links between those organisations and INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC activities. This should lead to an active engagement with relevant organisations and advocacy groups.

For the identification of relevant patient organisations WP5 could draw on already existing contacts and interactions of INFRAFRONTIER members, e.g. through common research activities. Using these interactions as a starting point, a systematic mapping of potentially relevant patient organisations and patient advocacy groups was carried out.

The analysis of the survey results was used as input for the setting the agendas for the larger IPAD-MD Stakeholder Engagement Workshops.

Methodology

In March 2016, we carried out a survey among the IPAD-MD partner about existing contacts to patient organisations and advocacy groups. The resulting list was complemented by the results of a targeted internet research.

The survey concentrated on patient organisations / advocacy groups with a confirmed reference to biomedical research activities, because they either

- had a link to research activities of INFRAFRONTIER partners;
- referred to biomedical research in their mission statement;
- referred to / provided information on animal / mouse models relevant to their disease area;
- provided an ethics statement referring to research with animal models on their websites; or
- provided funding for biomedical research projects

Patient organisations that didn't have links to biomedical research in either of the above categories were excluded from the survey results.

Survey Results

As shown in *Table 1* and *Figure 1*, 45 patient organisations were identified which could be mapped to 13 different disease areas. Among the disease areas represented, rare diseases, cancer and metabolic diseases were the most represented.

Table 1: Patient organisations with relations to biomedical research – Summary of the mapped disease areas

Research Area	Number of Patient Organisations Identified	Percentage of Disease Areas
Rare diseases	16	36%

Research Area	Number of Patient Organisations Identified	Percentage of Disease Areas
Cancer	7	16%
Metabolism	6	13%
Cardiovascular	2	4%
Ear	2	4%
Immunology	2	4%
Neurodegenerative diseases	2	4%
Skin	2	4%
Cystic Fibrosis	2	4%
Other Diseases (Albinism, Asthma, Bone, Eye)	4	9%
Total	45	100%

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Fig. 1: Percentage of disease areas represented by the identified patient organisations.

Table 2 lists all identified patient organisations, including website information as available, the country they are active in and their link to biomedical research activities.

Three organisations in the area of rare diseases are categorised as umbrella organisations, i.e. their link to biomedical research activities may come through the individual patient organisations they represent. They may, however, as is the case for EURORDIS, actively encourage or support research activities (cf. Annex 1: EURORDIS Position Paper on Research Priorities).

Table 2: List of all patient organisations identified in the survey

Research Area	Patient Organisation	Country	Link to Biomedical Research Activities
Albinism	ALBA www.albinismo.es	ES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Albinism	GENESPOIR www.genespoir.org	FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Albinism	ALBINIT www.albinit.org	IT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Asthma	Asthma UK www.asthma.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects
Bone	National Osteoporosis Foundation	US	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects
Cancer	Cancer Research www.cancerresearchuk.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects
Cancer	Leukaemia Research Fund www.leukemia-research.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Cancer	NCRN National Cancer Research Network	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models

Research Area	Patient Organisation	Country	Link to Biomedical Research Activities
Cancer	World Cancer Research Fund	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides statement on animal ethics • Funds research projects
Cancer	The Prostate Cancer Charity www.prostatecanceruk.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models
Cancer	NTRAC National Translational Cancer Research Network www.tcrn.unsw.edu.au	UK?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models
Cardiovascular	British Heart Foundation www.bhf.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Provides statement on animal ethics • Funds research projects
Cardiovascular	Heart Research UK www.heartresearch.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects
Ear	British Tinnitus Association www.tinnitus.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects
Ear	Action on Hearing Loss www.actiononhearingloss.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Provides statement on animal ethics

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Research Area	Patient Organisation	Country	Link to Biomedical Research Activities
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Funds research projects
Eye	National Eye Research Centre www.nerc-charity.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities Provides statement on animal ethics
Immunology- Inflammation	Arthritis Research Campaign www.arthritisresearchuk.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities Provides information about relevant mouse models Funds research projects
Immunology- Inflammation	British Society for Immunology	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities Provides information about relevant mouse models
Metabolism - Diabetes	Diabetes UK www.diabetes.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities Provides information about relevant mouse models Provides statement on animal ethics Funds research projects
Metabolism - Kidney	The PKD Charity www.pkdcharity.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities Funds research projects
Metabolism - Kidney	Kidney Research UK www.kidneyresearchuk.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities Provides information about relevant mouse models Funds research projects
Metabolism - Kidney	National Kidney Research Fund www.kidneyresearchuk.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities Provides information about relevant mouse models

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Research Area	Patient Organisation	Country	Link to Biomedical Research Activities
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides statement on animal ethics • Funds research projects
Metabolism - Liver	British Liver Trust www.britishlivertrust.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Metabolism - Liver	Childrens Liver Disease Foundation www.childliverdisease.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Neuro	Brain Research Trust www.brt.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Neuro	Spinal Research UK www.spinal-research.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects
Neuro	Motor Neuron Disease Association		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Neuro	Muscular Dystrophy Campaign www.muscular dystrophyuk.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Neuro - Parkinson's	Parkinson's Disease Society	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Provides statement on animal ethics
Neuro- Alzheimers	Alzheimer's Society www.alzheimers.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models

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Research Area	Patient Organisation	Country	Link to Biomedical Research Activities
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides statement on animal ethics • Funds research projects
Rare Disease	Ring 14 www.ring14.org	FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects
Rare Disease	Association Prader Willy France: www.prader-willy.fr	FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Rare Disease	Association Française des Syndromes Costello	FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides information about relevant mouse models
Rare Disease	Xtraordinaire www.xtraordinaire.org	FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Rare Diseases: Children Dementia	www.ncl-stiftung.de	DE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Rare Diseases: Charge Syndrome	www.charge-syndrom.de/	DE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities
Rare Disease	Foundation Fondation Jérôme Lejeune www.fondationlejeune.org/en/	FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Rare Disease	Care for rare DE	DE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides information about relevant mouse models
Rare Disease	Allianz Chronischer Seltener Erkrankungen www.achse-online.de	DE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funds research projects
Rare Disease - Gauchers Disease	Gauchers Association www.gaucher.org.uk/home	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides information about relevant mouse models • Funds research projects

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Research Area	Patient Organisation	Country	Link to Biomedical Research Activities
Rare Disease -Ataxia Telangiectasia	Action for AT	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Provides statement on animal ethics
Rare Diseases	Rare diseases UK http://www.raredisease.org.uk/ UMBRELLA ASSOCIATION	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in research activities as umbrella organisation
Rare Diseases	EURORDIS www.eurordis.org/ UMBRELLA ASSOCIATION	EU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in research activities as umbrella organisation
Rare Diseases	Foundation Maladies Rares www.fondation-maladiesrares.org/accueil	FR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Rare Diseases	Seltene Krankheiten AT http://www.seltenekrankheit.at/ UMBRELLA ASSOCIATION	AT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involvement in research activities as umbrella organisation
Skin	Raynauds and Scleroderma Association www.raynauds.org.uk/	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Skin - Epidermis Bulbosa	Debra www.debra.org	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Cystic Fibrosis	Cystic Fibrosis Foundation www.cff.org	US	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects
Cystic Fibrosis	Cystic Fibrosis Trust www.cysticfibrosis.org.uk	UK	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link to INFRAFRONTIER partner research activities • Funds research projects

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Conclusions from the survey

The main source of input to this survey were existing contacts to patient organisations stemming from our INFRAFRONTIER partners' research collaborations. This is because even though there are many patient advocacy groups in each of the European countries and globally, most of them operate only on a local / national level and do not provide any information about their position towards or engagement with basic research involving animal models. Since patient organisations usually rely on charitable funding, they often fear that an open support for animal research may threaten their funding model.

The following steps for engaging patient organisations are therefore suggested:

1. Patient organisations in the area of rare diseases, cancer, and metabolic diseases are most prevalent when it comes to their linking / support of biomedical research activities. INFRAFRONTIER's engagement activities should therefore focus on these areas.
2. Whenever possible, INFRAFRONTIER's engagement activities with patient organisations should leverage the existing links to INFRAFRONTIER partners.
3. Particularly in the area of rare diseases, INFRAFRONTIER's engagement should involve umbrella organisations such as EURORDIS.

2. Summary Report on the Engagement with Stakeholder Organisations

Summary of stakeholder engagement activities in IPAD-MD

During the course of the IPAD-MD project 4 large stakeholder engagement events took place. The stakeholder events in 2017–2019 were co-organised with the INFRAFRONTIER2020 project, but it was the role of the IPAD-MD to facilitate the input of and alignment with the International Mouse Phenotyping Consortium (IMPC).

- 1. INFRAFRONTIER Industry & Innovation Workshop, Munich** in June 2016. The main stakeholders targeted were representatives from industry and SMEs and the thematic focus therefore, lay on a) showcasing novel and innovative technologies to improve the phenotypic analysis of mouse models of human diseases, and b) on obtaining feedback from industry users on how to improve the utility of rodent models in the application of their R&D activities. The main results of this workshop have been reported in D2.1.
- 2. INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2017, Athens** in November 2017. This meeting targeted mainly stakeholders from two thematic areas: personalised medicine and rare diseases research. The participation of representatives from the European Medicines Agency highlighted regulatory aspects in the area of personalised medicine. The cross-cutting topic of responsible research and animal welfare also contained insights on how commercial companies approach this topic in their R&D activities from an EFPIA

(European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations) representative. The main results of this meeting have been reported in D2.3.

3. INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Stakeholder Meeting 2018,

Munich in December 2018. This meeting resumed a thematic focus on rare diseases as in the previous stakeholder event, and complemented this with the topic of gene therapy. In the rare diseases' session, the input of the ERA-Net E-Rare was of particular interest, since it provided information on the upcoming European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD) where INFRAFRONTIER is one of the research infrastructure partners. The topic of gene therapy provided information on projects from both the academic and the private sector. An ESFRI representative provided important insights on current developments in European science policy in the area of the research infrastructures. The main results of this meeting have been reported in D2.5.

4. INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC Conference 2019, Helsinki in June 2019. This last stakeholder event focused thematically on genetic variation and on ageing research, but brought in aspects of big data to both topics. In the sessions on genetic variation several Scandinavian initiatives to study disease complexes prevalent in specific communities were presented. Related to the ageing research focus, the LIFETIME project presented the approaches of this novel FET-flagship initiative on targeting single-cell trajectories across the human life-span. The main results of this conference have been summarised in D2.7.

A common theme of all these stakeholder events was to explore the contribution and value of rodent models to the topics and scientific areas addressed, to invite novel, innovative and interesting projects and initiatives in these respective fields, to bring in inputs from different fields like regulatory affairs, science policy and from the private sector and generally to obtain feedback on how to improve the large-scale mouse resources provided by INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC to a global user community.

Summary of INFRAFRONTIER activities targeting focal patient organisation and patient advocacy groups

The conclusions of D5.1 - Survey on Patient Organisations' Research Priorities, were to focus the engagement activities on patient organisations and advocacy groups from specific areas, namely rare diseases, cancer and metabolic diseases, to leverage existing links to INFRAFRONTIER partners and to engage with umbrella organisations like EURORDIS in the area of rare diseases were possible.

In the course of organising the IPAD-MD stakeholder events it became obvious that particularly the latter recommendation provided a workable approach: EURORDIS as a pan-European umbrella organisation in the field of rare diseases has the critical mass in terms of organisation to interact / cooperate with large-scale initiatives such as IRDiRC (International Rare Diseases Research Consortium) and the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD) and therefore, also has the understanding and band-width to interact with pan-European RIs and large-scale research initiatives such as INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC.

Addressing and inviting smaller patient organisations proved less fruitful, since even those organisations with existing links to INFRAFRONTIER partners were usually only interested in very specific projects and not in the broader topics addressed in the INFRAFRONTIER / IMPC stakeholder events.

In the following, we summarise recent INFRAFRONTIER activities that facilitate the interaction with patient organisation, particularly in the field of rare diseases and cancer research:

1. Since January 2019, INFRAFRONTIER is a partner in the EC funded programme European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (EJP-RD). This programme enables direct interactions with rare disease related patient organisations such as EURORDIS, which is also a partner in EJP-RD.
2. In 2019, INFRAFRONTIER was represented at the RE(ACT) Conference, International Congress on Research of Rare and Orphan Diseases, in Toronto, Canada. This conference targets both researchers as well as patients and patient organisations committed to research. INFRAFRONTIER will also contribute to further RE(ACT) Conferences, the one scheduled in Berlin in June 2020 had to be cancelled unfortunately due to the CORONA pandemic.
3. The INFRAFRONTIER Conference 2020, which we currently organise to take place in Brussels in October 2020, will have a focus on cancer research using animal models and how these activities align with the designated

Cancer Mission in Horizon Europe. We will use the survey on patient organisations with links to cancer research to target potential invitees.